

Fractography of Carbon/Epoxy Angle-Ply Laminates

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ABSTRACT

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and X-Ray radiography have been used to obtain information on the fracture behaviour of carbon fiber/epoxy (T300/1034) angle-ply laminates for angles $\pm \theta = 5, 15, 30$ and 45° . In order to understand the process leading to ultimate failure, failure event sequences were recorded during the tensile test, using motordriven cameras, taking six frames per second.

Damage growth in the form of matrix cracking and delamination initiates at different load levels relative to ultimate tensile load for the different ply angles. Damage initiates early for the ± 15 -deg specimens which are well-known for strong free edge effects.

The amount of delamination and matrix cracking in the failed specimens, as could be seen using the X-Ray technique, varied significantly with the ply angle.

The SEM-studies and the X-Ray photographs showed that debonding of fibers from the resin precedes delamination crack growth. As a result the delamination cracks grow parallel to the fiber directions of the plies lying adjacent to the resin-rich interlaminar regions. The characteristic serrated structure on the delaminated surfaces is explained as resulted from a combined action of interlaminar shear and tensile stresses.

INTRODUCTION

Experimental reports on the failure behaviour of finite width angle-ply laminates are rather scarce in the literature (1-3). Rotem and Hashin (1) investigated angle-ply laminates with ply angles, θ , ranging from 30 to 60° . Here three distinct failure modes could be identified. For angles $\theta < 45^\circ$ the failure mode was delamination, while for angles $\theta > 45^\circ$, ply failure was obtained. The $\theta = 45^\circ$ specimens showed a unique behaviour with a very high strain to failure.

Kim (2) investigated the strength of angle-ply laminates and compared the results with the tensor polynomial failure criterion developed by Tsai and Wu. Only moderate agreement with the experimental results was obtained.

Delamination during in-plane loading is a unique failure mode in composite laminates, it is generally attributed to out of plane shear and/or normal stresses that develops close to the laminate free edge. Elastic analyses using the finite-element of the finite difference methods (4-7) show that the inter-laminar stresses in angle-ply laminates are dominated by a single interlaminar shear stress, eg τ_{xz} . Altus et al (7) points out the possibility that also the interlaminar normal stress, σ_z , is a significant factor affecting interlaminar failure in angle-ply laminates. All analyses presented so far assumes the lamellae to be both homogenous and anisotropic. Laminate analysis after initial failure has occurred is prohibitively difficult.

This paper reports results obtained from tensile in-plane loading up to failure of carbon fibre/epoxy angle ply laminates for ply angles $\pm \theta = 5, 15, 30$ and 45° . In order to obtain information on the damage initiation and growth process leading to ultimate failure, the failure event sequences were recorded during the test using motordriven cameras. Post failure inspection of the specimens were made using scanning electronmicroscopy (SEM) and X-Ray radiography.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Unidirectional carbon/epoxy prepreg, T300/1034, with a matrix content of approximately 42 % by volume was used as raw material. The Fiberite system, Hy-E 1034, is essentially a tetraglycidyl 4,4' diaminodiphenyl methane epoxide (TGMDA or TGDDM) with curing agent 4,4' diaminodiphenyl sulfone (DDS) and a catalyst borontrifluorine monoethylamine ($\text{BF}_3\text{-MEA}$). It contains as a second epoxide diglycidylether of bisphenol A (DGEBA).

The prepreg materials were hand laid-up in the desired angles and fabricated following the manufacturer's recommended curing procedure. The final product was obtained as rectangular sheets with a matrix content of approximately 35 % from which the specimens were cut with a diamond wheel. The laminate thickness was 1 mm corresponding to eight prepreg layers laid up according to $[\pm\theta]_{2S}$ with $\theta = 5, 15, 30$ and 45° . The type of specimens used for the tensile testing is shown in Fig 1.

The testing equipment used was a computer controlled MTS closed-loop hydraulic testing machine. Failure event sequences were recorded using two motordriven cameras, taking six frames per second. One recorded events on the edge, and the other recorded events on the top surface of the specimens. The specimens were stretched at a constant displacement rate under displacement control. Post-failure examination of the specimens were made using Tetrabromoethane (TBE)-enhanced X-Ray photography.

Prior to SEM-examination the fractured specimens were cut with a diamond wheel to smaller pieces, and carbon was evaporated in vacuum onto the fracture surfaces to minimize static charging by the SEM electron beam. The microscope used for the fracture surface analysis was a Jeol JSM P15 scanning electron microscope.

RESULTS

The load-displacement curves are shown in Fig 2. The deformation behaviour of the laminates resembles at all angles (except the $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ -specimens) that of brittle materials (low strain to failure and failure at maximum load). For the $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ -specimens the materials behaviour was different with a higher strain to failure.

Failure Event Recordings (14)

First observable failure event occurs at different load levels relative to ultimate tensile load (UTL), see Fig. 3, for the different lay-up angles. Damage growth starts early for the ± 15 -deg specimens. These laminates are well-known for dominant free edge effects (3).

As could be seen from the edge, damage initiates for all laminates as

delamination (separation) and/or transverse matrix cracking of outer plies. The delamination and transverse cracking continues further at the inner plies. The exact manner by which this happens depends upon the lay-up angle. A developing crack path which is not far from parallel to the laminate plane can be seen at the edge of the ± 5 -deg specimens, Fig. 4a. For the ± 30 -deg specimens the crack path at the edge grows more or less perpendicular to the laminate plane, Fig. 4b. The ± 15 -deg specimens shows a behaviour which is a combination of the ± 5 and the ± 30 behaviour. The final failure for the ± 5 , ± 15 and the ± 30 -deg specimens is fiber breakage.

For the ± 45 -deg specimens transverse matrix cracking followed by delamination starts at 90 % of UTL (which is only fraction of the ultimate tensile elongation). Near fracture the resin is broken up so that the material consists of bundles of non-adherent fibres. (Fig. 4c) At final failure the plies are sheared a part with a limited amount of fiber breakage.

X-Ray Photography

Post-failure inspection of the specimens were made using Tetrabromoethane (TBE)-enhanced X-ray photography. Typical results are shown in Fig. 5. It can be seen that the fiber fracture surface is approximately parallel to the fiber directions for the ± 5 -deg specimens and roughly perpendicular to the loading axis for the ± 30 -deg specimens. The ± 15 -deg specimens show both kinds of behaviour while the ± 45 -deg specimens mainly fail by delamination and (transverse) matrix cracking. The matrix cracking generally involves both transverse and longitudinal cracks and is often seen to extend parallel to the fiber directions of the laminates. Debonding of fibers from the resin probably forms one important element of the matrix cracking. For the ± 5 -deg specimens the matrix cracks and delaminations are concentrated near the fiber fracture surfaces. For the ± 15 -deg specimens extensive matrix cracking and delamination occurs close to the fiber fracture surface and parallel to the fiber directions. The ± 30 -deg specimens shows a very limited amount of matrix cracking and delamination. Initiation points can be seen at the edge and close to the fiber fracture surface. For the ± 45 -deg specimens the matrix cracks and delamination has occurred in a coarse band at the specimen center. Again matrix cracking and delamination appears mainly to extend parallel to the fiber directions.

SEM-Results

A number of fiber fracture surfaces were studied in the SEM. Figs. 6-7 shows typical results. It can be seen that the surfaces all show a "brittle" appearance with a relatively small amount of fiber pull-out, indicating a relatively high interfacial bond strength between fiber and matrix. On the other hand, the fiber surfaces were generally free of matrix residues indicating weak interfacial bonding. The individual fiber fracture surfaces are irregular but are often symmetric from the perimeter towards the center, indicating tensile failure.

A special interest was laid upon studies of delamination fracture surfaces. In Fig. 8 one notices the distinct impressions of fibers which have debonded (delaminated) from the resin. These impressions are seen in the epoxy matrix still covering the fibers in the ply underneath. Between these impressions, the characteristic structure of the plastically deformed epoxy matrix can be seen. These structures were first reported by Chamis and Sinclair (8) who named them "lacerations" and related them to fracture by tearing that results from intra-laminar shear. They are also known as "hackles" and have been used for determining fracture directions and fracture origins in quasi-isotropic and unidirectional laminates (9). They are also identified as "serrations" observed in fatigue of off-axis carbon/epoxy laminates (10). The term "serrations" will be used throughout. Important to notice in Fig. 8 is that serrations lie between debonded fibers and are always oriented more or less normal to the debonded fiber axes.

The fracture surface in Fig. 8 may be called "resin rich" as almost no fibers are exposed to the electron beam.

An example of a delamination surface with relatively less resin residues ("resin poor") is shown in Fig. 9. In this case uncovered fibers are seen with some characteristic resin structure in between. In some of the fracture surfaces resin rich areas were dominating (Fig. 8), in other cases resin poor areas like in Fig. 9 dominated. This appearance seems to reflect the fact that there are two preferred paths for the delamination crack to propagate, one near each ply on both sides of the interlaminar region.

In Fig. 10a and b two mating delamination surfaces are shown. One should observe that extensive formation of serrations on one surface corresponds to a more featureless structure on the mating surface. This was often found to be the case and implies that delamination cracking close to one or the other of the two plies with different fiber orientation, resulting in a two-planar delamination surface.

Fig. 11a and b shows a delamination fracture surface studied in the SEM with the surface at 90° and 30° , respectively, to the electron beam. The impressions from the fibers belonging to the +5⁰ lamina are seen on the surface and one broken fiber from this lamina is left on the fracture surface. One should notice the sheet-like character of the plastically deformed epoxy matrix, these sheets being pulled in a more or less upright position. Careful inspection of Fig. 11b leads one to the conclusion that formation of serrations in this case actually has taken place in between fibers in the outermost sheet of +5⁰ ply, rather than in the resin-rich interlaminar region.

DISCUSSION

Visible damage growth for the different lay-up angles initiates at 50 to 90 % of UTL. The early damage initiation and the continuous deterioration of the ± 15 -deg specimens during straining explains the poor applicability of failure criteria (where perfect bonding of the plies are assumed) since the specimen in parts consists of uncoupled plies prior to ultimate failure. See also Fig. 5 where the damage is significant for the ± 15 -deg specimens, but somewhat less for the ± 5 -deg and the ± 30 -deg specimens.

The X-Ray photographs imply that damage in the form of matrix cracks and delaminations preferentially grows along the fiber directions. Delamination cracking along the fiber directions is understood if debonding of the fibers from the resin precedes delamination. These debonded areas provide a low energy path for crack propagation.

The SEM photographs show that delamination cracking involves matrix cracking and debonding of fibers from the matrix. Delamination cracking occurs close to one or the other layer of fibers resulting in a two-planar fracture surface. Delamination cracks grow parallel to the fiber directions. These results are important when e.g. calculating the strain energy release rate for delamination crack growth which normally assumes microscopic homogeneity, and a crack completely embedded in the resin rich interlaminar region (12).

Matrix cracking occurs in the form of serrations. The serrated structure is generally attributed to shear stresses (8, 10) but also a Mode I crack growth explanation has been attempted (9). Results obtained from fractography of thermoplastics show that apparent similar structures are formed by tensile fracture of shear bands (11). It is well known that epoxy resins are not highly crosslinked because of steric and diffusional restrictions during polymerization and network formation (13). It was shown in (13) that TGMDA-DDS epoxies fracture at room temperature to some extent by shear banding. This mode of deformation becomes prominent at higher temperatures and is responsible for the high strain to failure near T_g . The following simplified model for the formation of serrations is thus suggested (Fig. 12).

Fig. 12 (a) shows a sideview of the undeformed interlaminar matrix region between plies close to one or the other layers of fibers. Fig. 12 (b) shows this

region under shear deformation. Debonding of fibers from the resin precedes delamination and occurs due to shear stresses at the interface. Shear strain in the matrix will also tend to align with the fiber direction since this is the line of least resistance. Microcracking and shear yielding of the matrix occurs as the strains exceeds the elastic limit. The microcracks grows further due to an interlaminar tensile stress, σ_z (Fig. 12c). Delamination finally occurs close to the fibers due to a combined action of interlaminar tensile and shear stresses. The orientation of serrations thus indicates the direction of shear as well as the direction of delamination crack growth.

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Fig. 1 Geometry of test specimens

Fig. 2 Load-elongation curves of angle ply laminates

Fig. 3 Initiation - load of first visible damage/ultimate tensile load (UTL) vs ply angle, θ .

Fig. 4 Edge damage just before final failure
 a) $\pm 5^{\circ}$ b) $\pm 15^{\circ}$ c) $\pm 45^{\circ}$

Fig. 5 X-Ray photographs of failed specimens
 a) $\pm 5^{\circ}$ b) $\pm 15^{\circ}$ c) $\pm 30^{\circ}$ d) $\pm 45^{\circ}$

Fig. 6 Fiber fracture surface (general view), $\pm 30^\circ$

Fig. 7 Fiber fracture surfaces (detailed view), $\pm 30^\circ$

Fig. 8 Delaminated fracture surface, resin rich region.

Fig. 9 Delaminated fracture surface, resin poor region.

Fig. 10 Mating delamination surfaces, $\pm 15^\circ$. Identical points on the two surfaces are denoted A and B, respectively

Fig. 11 a) Delaminated surface for a ± 5 -deg laminate
 b) Same as a) bur surface tilted 60° . Identical points on the surface are denoted A and B, respectively

Fig. 12 Formation of serrations in composite laminates

